

Approval of ethical and legal conformance of eCREAM tools

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Responsible partner: ECRIN

Prepared by: Maria A. Rujano (ECRIN), Mihaela Matei (ECRIN)

Contributors: Sergio Contrino (ECRIN), Giulia Irene Ghilardi (IRFMN), Chiara Pandolfini (IRFMN), Sergej Černič (UKCM), Justyna Danel (UJ).

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

CHUV	Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois, Switzerland
DPO	Data Protection Officer
eCREAM	Enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine through automated data extraction
ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
ED	Emergency Department
EHR	Electronic health record
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FBK	Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Italy
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GR	Greece
IRB	Institutional Review Board
IRFMN	Istituto Di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri IRCCS, Italy
IT	Italy
LM	Language Model
MIP	Medical Information Platform
NLP	Natural Language Processing
Orobix	Orobix Life SRL, Italy
PL	Poland
SI	Slovenia
UC1	Use Case 1
UC2	Use Case 2
UK	United Kingdom
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The eCREAM project addresses the critical need for continuous assessment and improvement of emergency departments (EDs) to ensure timely and effective patient care. By leveraging electronic health records (EHRs) and advanced natural language processing (NLP) tools, eCREAM aims to overcome the challenges such as high patient volumes and staff shortages that currently limit clinical research in emergency medicine. The project will develop innovative technical solutions to extract valuable clinical information from EHRs, enabling the creation of high-quality databases on patients attending emergency departments across multiple sites and countries.

This document represents Milestone M14 - Approval of Ethical and Legal Conformance of eCREAM Tools. It outlines the steps taken to ensure that all activities and tools involving personal data processing comply with applicable legal, regulatory, and ethical frameworks. Where applicable, supporting documentation is referenced to demonstrate conformity, including study protocols, data protection assessments, and relevant project deliverables or milestone reports. While some approvals are still pending due to varying national review timelines, the consortium is actively coordinating with local partners to complete all necessary processes prior to the launch of data collection activities.

Project context

The eCREAM project aims to enhance the quality and efficiency of emergency department (ED) care by developing innovative tools to extract structured clinical information from electronic health records (EHRs), including both structured and unstructured data. Leveraging artificial intelligence and natural language processing (NLP), the project supports the creation of high-quality, interoperable databases that can be used to improve clinical research, healthcare delivery, and public health decision-making.

By facilitating sustainable, large-scale data extraction without additional burden on healthcare staff, eCREAM aims to overcome existing research limitations in emergency medicine. The project prioritizes strict adherence to ethical, legal, and data protection standards, ensuring that all activities comply with relevant European and national regulations.

Milestone context and importance

To meet the objectives of the eCREAM project, the following activities have been performed or are underway:

- Retrospective cohort study for the development and validation of a natural language processing tool (NLP-DeVal) to enable clinical research in emergency and acute care medicine.
- An observational retrospective quality-of-care study to develop two statistical models to estimate the propensity to hospitalize patients arriving at the ED with dyspnoea or after transient loss of consciousness (TLoC) (Use case 1)
- An observational retrospective study to develop dashboards for monitoring emergency department operations and emerging epidemiological trends (Use case 2)

These activities involve the processing of personal and clinical data extracted from both structured (organized and easily searchable data such as demographic details, vital signs, diagnostic codes, medications and lab results) and unstructured (free text or images, i.e., medical images and written narratives, including clinical notes, problem lists, discharge summaries and radiology reports) data from electronic health records (EHRs).

This milestone marks a significant step toward ensuring that eCREAM activities align with relevant ethical principles and legal frameworks for the processing of sensitive health data. It reflects the achievement of formal approvals at several clinical sites, and the validation that these activities meet the requirements of key regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), national laws governing health data, and ethical standards for AI use in healthcare.

Given the cross-border nature of the project, spanning Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia and the United Kingdom, navigating divergent regulatory landscapes and ethical review processes has posed considerable challenges. Differences in local interpretations of GDPR, data governance structures, and ethics committee procedures have required tailored approaches in each country. This milestone shows substantial progress toward establishing the ethical and legal foundations necessary for performing these activities, while efforts continue to secure final approvals at the remaining sites. This progress is critical for enabling the next phases of the project, including broader data access, tools implementation and validation.

Overview of eCREAM activities requiring the use of data and Ethical and Legal Approval

A brief description of the primary use of the data, and the types of personal or clinical data used for development of tools and the implementation of eCREAM activities is provided in the table below.

Table 1. eCREAM activities involving the processing of personal and clinical data

Activity	Use of personal data	Data pseudonymised	Data anonymised
NLP-DeVal	Non-annotated (millions) and annotated (8,000) clinical notes derived from EHRs		Unstructured, retrospective data, cleaned up of any possible sensitive data
Use Case 1	Clinical data from existing EHRs and other patient records. Patient characteristics upon arrival at the ED. Collected only on patients with dyspnoea or Transient loss of consciousness	Structured and unstructured retrospective data	
Use Case 2	Clinical data obtained from EHRs. Real time data on all patients who visited the EDs between July 1, 2023, and December 31, 2023		Structured retrospective data

Legal Compliance

Due to the sensitive nature of the data necessary for the development of the eCREAM activities, the collection, analysis, sharing and transfer of such data requires a comprehensive analysis of the applicable legal, regulatory and ethical frameworks governing these data processing activities.

This task is further complicated by the cross-border nature of the project, involving data workflows across five European countries: Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, and the United Kingdom. While the GDPR provides a unified baseline for data protection, it allows for national adaptations in the legal requirements for the processing of health-related data. As a result, the legal frameworks and interpretations of GDPR provisions vary significantly across Member States, leading to diverse national requirements. Therefore, a dedicated legal task force was established under WP5 to identify the relevant national laws and regulations applicable to eCREAM.

Another challenge specific to the project is the fact that the use of data through the eCREAM innovative tools does not fall under standard practice. Consequently, data providers and data users are operating in a rather grey area from a legal and regulatory perspective. Identifying a clear and compliant legal framework for these activities was therefore a critical early step, achieved through an extensive legal review and analysis.

Based on this work, the following key legal, regulatory and ethical requirements have been identified:

1. GDPR Compliance

- A. Data processing activities outside the scope of the GDPR: no further legal requirements under the GDPR

For practical reasons and not to block the project activities, it has been decided to anonymise the information collected to feed the dashboards (UC2) as well as the data necessary to develop and validate the NLP tool. Consequently, the data processing activities used for the development of the language model and the dashboards do not fall under the GDPR. Nevertheless, the process of anonymisation is considered a personal data processing activity. The responsibility for anonymising the data prior to sharing it lies with the initial data provider (i.e., hospitals) and not with the developers of the tool. Through the contracting process, the responsibilities of the data provider versus data receiver have been clarified. In certain countries (e.g. Greece, Italy) permissions are required for the anonymisation of personal data (permissions by the Ethics Committees and by the Hospital which provides the data). In Greece, an opinion of the DPO of the Ministry of Health can be required. No specific authorisations or permissions are required for the data receiver to process anonymised data.

- B. Data processing activities falling under the scope of the GDPR:

In the context of UC1, data cannot be anonymised for two main reasons: first, the data originally collected by healthcare professionals in a non-systematic and heterogeneous manner may contain missing values and inconsistencies; and second, applying anonymisation techniques would compromise their utility for analysis. As a result, the data fall under the scope of the GDPR (Rec. 26 GDPR), and to preserve its integrity and utility for research while ensuring legal compliance, the database will be pseudonymised prior to transfer. The project implements several safeguards to protect data subjects' rights and welfare, including removal or masking of personal identifiers, Ethics Committee approvals, legal consultations with Data Protection Officers or legal department representatives of each partner, drafting of the Data Protection Impact Assessment required by some countries and its public communication via institutional websites. The principle of data minimization and robust data security are strictly enforced. Additionally, the project complies with country-specific data protection laws, including those of non-EU partners like the UK.

As part of ensuring full alignment with the GDPR and other applicable legal, regulatory, and institutional frameworks, the eCREAM consortium has undertaken a structured process to secure the necessary clearances required for the processing of sensitive health data. These activities have been carried out primarily within WP1 (NLP) and WP4 (Use Cases), with close involvement of national partners and legal experts.

The approvals fall into three main categories: authorisations, permissions, and ethical opinions. These are required not only under the GDPR, but also under national data protection laws, medical research regulations, and institutional governance policies. Specifically:

- Authorisations refer to formal legal or regulatory approvals from a governmental or regulatory authority (e.g. Data Protections Authorities, Health Ministries) which are required for collecting, processing or transferring sensitive health data.
- Permissions refer to institutional or data owner-level (e.g. hospitals, PIs, sponsors, data governance committees, patients) approvals, operational or technical access rights that control what actions users can perform on patient data, such as viewing, editing, or sharing records, and are usually managed according to organisational roles and technical protocols.

- Ethical opinions are formal assessments provided by Ethics Committees or Institutional Review Boards (IRB) to evaluate the ethical implications of the research or secondary use of data, particularly in relation to data protection, consent, and risk to individuals.

The following tables summarise the authorisations, permissions and opinions required for the activities involving personal data, and the corresponding legal provisions applicable in the countries concerned.

NLP-DeVal

Legal basis for processing: Scientific research purposes under GDPR Article 9(2)(j) in conjunction with Article 89(1), with appropriate safeguards including anonymisation.

Table 2. Authorisations, permissions and opinions required for NLP-DeVal

Country	GR	IT	PL	SI	UK
Number of Sites	5	17	2	1	3
Authorisation Required	No	No	No	No	No
Permissions Required	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Ethical Opinion Required	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Data Processing & Transfer Agreements	Yes	Yes		Yes	No
Technical & Organisational Measures	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes

Specific comments:
GR: In the case of the transfer of anonymized data, specific permission by the ethics committee of each hospital concerned and an opinion of the hospital’s DPO are also required before the anonymization operation. Again, an opinion of the DPO of the Ministry of Health can be required. In any case, Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union is also applied after anonymizing the data.
PL: Before submitting an application for ethics committee approval, a separate approval for each study protocol is required from every participating institution (following the opinion of the institution’s Data Protection Officer). The application must then be reviewed and accepted by the Jagiellonian University ethics committee, which will issue an opinion on whether approval from a higher-level institution is also required. As of now:
 - Military Hospital – approvals obtained for all three study protocols; ethics application can proceed.
 - University Hospital – reviewing documentation; requested Military Hospital approvals and an ethics approval from another participating site before granting their own.
SI: In hospital the Medical Ethics committee University Medical Centre Maribor gave the project consensus. Also, the National one with number of approval: 0120-117/2025-2711-3. The DPO is part of the eCcream project, so no specific permissions further are required.

UC1

Legal basis for processing: Scientific research carried out in the public interest, based on GDPR Art. 9(2)(j) and Art. 89(1). Consent is not required due to disproportionate effort, given the retrospective nature and large sample size of the study, which make recontacting individuals impractical and potentially introduce bias. Safeguards include pseudonymisation, ethics committee approval, and notification via institutional channels.

Table 3. Authorisations, permissions and opinions required for UC1

Country	IT	PL	SI	UK
Number of Sites	17	2	1	3
Authorisation Required	No	No	No	No
Permissions Required	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Ethical Opinion Required	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Data Processing & Transfer Agreements	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Technical & Organisational Measures	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Specific comments: IT: Application of Art. 100 D.lgs. n. 196/2003 SI: Number of approval from national ethical committee: 0120-256/2025-2711-4				

UC2

Legal basis for processing: Anonymised data used for scientific research purposes falls outside the scope of GDPR (Recital 26). Where identifiable data are processed prior to anonymization, the legal basis is GDPR Art. 9(2)(j) in conjunction with Art. 89(1), which permits processing for scientific research without consent, provided appropriate safeguards are in place. Each centre acts as data controller and is responsible for applying the anonymisation process. Informed consent is obtained only for participants involved in questionnaire-based evaluation of the dashboards.

Table 4. Authorisations, permissions and opinions required for UC2

Country	IT	PL	SI	UK
Number of Sites	17	2	1	3
Authorisation Required	No	No	No	No
Permissions Required	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Ethical Opinion Required	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Data Processing & Transfer Agreements	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Technical & Organisational Measures	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Specific comments: SI: Number of approval from national ethical committee: 0120-256/2025-2711-4				

2. ELSI Document and Legal Framework

The eCREAM consortium prepared a comprehensive ELSI (Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications) Document (D5.1, Appendix 2)¹, developed by the legal working group. This document is intended to identify the legal and regulatory steps required to perform the consortium activities, the conditions that the Beneficiary of the project must comply with to ensure a lawful data collection and processing within the project’s scope, etc. It has served as a basis for the Regulatory submissions and contracting.

Overview of the ELSI Document:

Purpose:

- To describe the data that will be collected and processed within the scope of eCREAM and the corresponding data flows.
- To define the legal basis for data processing under EU and national frameworks.
- To propose solutions to collect and process these data in a safe and legal way, in accordance with European and national legal frameworks.
- To support each national partner in engaging with local ethics committees or authorities.
- To define the legal framework for the study protocol used in partner institutions.

¹ Banzi, R., Contrino, S., Guilardi, G. I., Matei, M., Rujano, M. A., & Schaffhauser, B. (2024). eCREAM Draft Data-Sharing Management Plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10853659>

Legal Basis Identified:

- Scientific research under Article 6(1)(e) and 9(2)(j) of the GDPR.
- Special category data processing based on public interest in the area of public health and research exemptions.

Data Flows Covered:

1. NLP-DeVal: participating hospitals retrospectively collect clinical data, which is anonymised locally using the eCREAM NLP platform. Once anonymised, the data is transferred to the Central eCREAM server, where it may be made accessible beyond the project consortium, including to partners such as FBK, Orobix, or through open access repositories.
2. Use case 1: hospitals collect retrospective clinical data, pseudonymise it locally, and process it via the eCREAM-UC1 platform. The resulting datasets are then transferred to the Central eCREAM server, where they are aggregated to form the UC1 study database. After curation, the database may be made available through the Medical Informatics Platform (MIP), a collaborative tool managed by CHUV that federates access to patient data across multiple hospitals.
3. Use case 2: retrospective data is extracted and processed within each hospital's information system using the local eCREAM UC2 platform. After anonymization at the local level, the data is securely transferred to the Central eCREAM server for further analysis.

Mitigation Measures:

- Data minimization, pseudonymisation and anonymisation at source.
- Legal basis validation by national legal contacts.
- Templates for consent (UC2), DTA, and study protocols harmonised across partners.

Further details on data types, legal basis, and safeguards are provided in the relevant sections of this milestone, in D5.1 - Draft Data Sharing Management Plan², M13 - FAIRification strategy for eCREAM outputs³ and Study Protocols^{4,5,6}.

3. Legal and operational questionnaire

To complement the legal framework established by the ELSI document and ensure clarity on applicable legal and regulatory requirements, the WP5 team developed a dedicated legal and operational questionnaire (D5.1, Appendix 3⁷) that addresses key operational and legal aspects related to the processing of patient-related data within participating hospitals.

² Banzi, R., Contrino, S., Guilardi, G. I., Matei, M., Rujano, M. A., & Schaffhauser, B. (2024). eCREAM Draft Data-Sharing Management Plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10853659>

³ Rujano, M. A. (2024). FAIRification strategy for eCREAM outputs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13780213>

⁴ Bertolini, G., Ghilardi, G. I., Pandolfini, C., Nattino, G., Lavelli, A., & Moretti, F. (2024). Study protocol - NLP-DeVal: Development and validation of a natural language processing tool to enable clinical research in emergency and acute care medicine: retrospective cohort study. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10996542>

⁵ Bertolini, G., Banzi, R., Catania, F., Lavelli, A., Ghilardi, G. I., Pandolfini, C., & Nattino, G. (2024). Study protocol - Propensity to hospitalize patients from the ED in European centers An observational retrospective quality-of-care study. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10996665>

⁶ Bertolini, G., Ghilardi, G. I., Pandolfini, C., Nattino, G., Catania, F., & Banzi, R. (2024). Study protocol - Development of a multipurpose dashboard to monitor the situation of emergency departments. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10996699>

⁷ Banzi, R., Contrino, S., Guilardi, G. I., Matei, M., Rujano, M. A., & Schaffhauser, B. (2024). eCREAM Draft Data-Sharing Management Plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10853659>

The responses collected through this questionnaire served as a foundation to (a) develop the project’s Data-Sharing Management Plan (Deliverable D.5.1), and (b) assist all involved partners in identifying and fulfilling the specific legal and regulatory obligations under the GDPR and relevant national laws and regulations. These efforts ensured that data processing activities within eCREAM are aligned with the complex and diverse legal requirements across different jurisdictions, supporting compliant and responsible data governance.

Ethical oversight and approvals

1. Ethics Advisory Board appointment

An Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) has been formally appointed to provide independent guidance on the ethical, legal, and societal aspects of the eCREAM project. The establishment of the EAB took longer than initially anticipated, but the board is now in place and has actively engaged with the consortium. Most recently, the EAB participated in the 2024 Consortium meeting, where members were introduced to the project’s objectives, data workflows, and ethical considerations.

Appointed members are:

Luca Marelli: Assistant professor at UNIMI and visiting fellow at KU Leuven. He is involved in several EU projects. One of his main areas of expertise/research is bioethics.

Irene Schlünder: lawyer and expert in EU data protection law and database governance. She works for the association Technology and Methods Platform for Networked Medical Research e.V. (TMF e.V.). She is involved in various national and European research projects. She collaborates with the EU Commission on the implementation of the upcoming European Health Data Space. Member of the ELSI Service & Research Unit of BBMRI-ERIC.

2. Ethics approval per country

Study protocols have been submitted to the relevant Ethics Committees or Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) in each participating country for the activities involving the processing of personal data. These approvals ensure that all activities uphold the rights, dignity, and safety of individuals whose data are used. Each protocol outlines the objectives, study design, methodology, monitoring procedures, ethical considerations, and quality assurance measures for the respective activity. The table below provides an overview of the submission and approval status of these protocols by country and tool.

Table 5. Overview of the submission and approval status of the protocols by country and tool

Country \ Activity	NLP		UC1		UC2	
	Submitted	Approved	Submitted	Approved	Submitted	Approved
GR	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
IT	17	13	14	7	14	7
PL	2	1	2	1	2	1
SI	1	1	1	1	1	1
UK	1	0	1	0	1	0

Documentation and Supporting Evidence

- Deliverable 5.1 – eCREAM Draft Data-Sharing Management Plan⁸, Appendix 2. Data flows and legal bases for data collection and processing, and Appendix 3. Operational and Legal Questionnaire.
- Deliverable 7.3 – Feedback from participants’ ethics advisory boards⁹
- Milestone 13 - FAIRification strategy for eCREAM outputs¹⁰.
- Study protocol - Development of a multipurpose dashboard to monitor the situation of emergency departments¹¹.
- Study protocol - Propensity to hospitalize patients from the ED in European centers. An observational retrospective quality-of-care study¹².
- Study protocol - NLP-DeVal: Development and validation of a natural language processing tool to enable clinical research in emergency and acute care medicine: retrospective cohort study¹³.

Next Steps

This milestone confirms that the project has established a solid ethical and legal foundation to support the commencement of data processing activities. While a number of ethics approvals have already been obtained at the national or institutional level, several others are still under review by the relevant competent authorities. The consortium is actively working with local partners to finalise the remaining approvals processes as soon as possible.

In parallel, the recently appointed EAB will conduct its first formal review of the project’s data governance framework, consent procedures, and compliance with ethical standards. This review will complement national ethics approvals and help ensure consistent ethical oversight across all participating countries.

Together, the completion of ethics approvals and the EAB’s input will enable the secure and compliant launch of data collection and processing activities under eCREAM.

Declaration

The eCREAM consortium affirms its full commitment to conducting all personal data processing activities in accordance with the GDPR, national data protection laws, and established ethical research standards.

⁸ Banzi, R., Contrino, S., Guilardi, G. I., Matei, M., Rujano, M. A., & Schaffhauser, B. (2024). eCREAM Draft Data-Sharing Management Plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10853659>

⁹ Pandolfini, C., Ghilardi, G. I., & Bertolini, G. (2025). Feedback from Participants' Ethics Advisory Boards. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16419348>

¹⁰ Rujano, M. A. (2024). FAIRification strategy for eCREAM outputs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13780213>

¹¹ Bertolini, G., Ghilardi, G. I., Pandolfini, C., Nattino, G., Catania, F., & Banzi, R. (2024). Study protocol - Development of a multipurpose dashboard to monitor the situation of emergency departments. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10996699>

¹² Bertolini, G., Banzi, R., Catania, F., Lavelli, A., Ghilardi, G. I., Pandolfini, C., & Nattino, G. (2024). Study protocol - Propensity to hospitalize patients from the ED in European centers. An observational retrospective quality-of-care study. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10996665>

¹³ Bertolini, G., Ghilardi, G. I., Pandolfini, C., Nattino, G., Lavelli, A., & Moretti, F. (2024). Study protocol - NLP-DeVal: Development and validation of a natural language processing tool to enable clinical research in emergency and acute care medicine: retrospective cohort study. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10996542>

MILESTONE 14 - Approval of ethical and legal conformance of eCREAM tools

At the time of this milestone, several required approvals from Ethics Committees, IRBs, and regulatory authorities have already been secured. For the remaining cases, submissions have been completed or are currently underway and under review. The approval process is progressing in line with national procedures, and no data processing will commence at any site until all necessary authorisations and permissions have been granted.

The consortium remains fully committed to upholding the rights, dignity, and privacy of all individuals whose data is involved in the project.